

Development of a web-based barangay management system with community charge sheet hotspotting

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Abstract

The system intends to automate a barangay's processes and transactions by using the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) methodology. The researchers presented the system to a panel of IT experts for evaluation following the development process. The system intends to aid barangay duty officers to make and keep electronic records, announcements, reports, and services, and help improve the response time when responding to the residents' needs. Residents can electronically fill out required forms for barangay certificates using the system. The system is expected to eliminate the need for residents to interact with barangay duty officers face-to-face. The implementation of the system will improve the barangay's overall services to its residents. The study was conducted in Talaba 2, Bacoor City. According to the findings of the evaluation, the researchers suggested that they make changes to the system.

Keywords: *Barangay; Barangay management system; Data analytics; Agile project management; Blotter records.*

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Introduction

Computer technology has become ingrained in modern society. Technology is being used by people all over the world to make various tasks easier to complete (Owan & Basse, 2018). Technology has made a significant contribution to the government sector. The use of computer technology has reaped significant benefits for various government units, particularly barangay units (Kononenko & Lutsenko, 2019). Barangays are the target audience for this capstone project. The technology is designed to automate transactions and processes inside the barangay. Most barangays have historically carried out their everyday operations and transactions by hand. They perform face-to-face transactions and use pen and paper to document them. In the current era of technology, this approach is no longer applicable. It is ineffective at giving residents satisfactory service and prone to human mistake (Carpio, 2020). There is a greater need to improve the system that the barangay and its residents use to operate and conduct transactions. The most effective way to address these concerns is to use an IT-based solution (FarajAllah et al., 2018; Imus et al., 2018). The researchers created an automated management system that barangays can use. All the problems and errors that occurred during the manual process can be eliminated by the said system.

This web-based system can benefit both parties—the barangay officials and the residents—because it can issue documents and collect data at any time and from any location (Bautista et al., 2023; Bringula et al., 2022; Jamis et al., 2022; Lacasandile et al., 2020). This is especially useful during a pandemic, because people can use their devices instead of pen and paper, which can help the community reduce waste such as paper as the information is already stored on the computer. The spread of communicable diseases is possible if pens will be continued to be used and barangay halls are frequently visited (Mathur et al., 2015).

This study aims to create a system that will allow people to advance technologically. With internet connection, authorized users can access the community web-based management system from anywhere at any time. This system is also accessible on any device that is transferred from one device to another, such as desktops, mobile phones, tablets, and so on, with no changes in features as long as web browsers are used to access it. This is certainly more convenient than the traditional method of the barangay official going to the barangay hall to serve his or her constituents.

Følstad (2017) claimed that one of the most important requirements in their field is proper document management. One of the obstacles to their efficiency is the lack of proper file organization. Furthermore, due to government protocol in response to the pandemic, residents in the area are having a difficult time getting the documents they require because they must go to the barangay, queue, and wait for the process to be completed. Some residents are unable to do these things because they are not permitted to leave their homes. People are unable to go to the barangay in their entirety due to social distancing and other government protocols.

The system was developed using the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) methodology. The researchers presented the system to a panel of IT experts for evaluation following the development process. Barangay duty officers will be able to create and maintain electronic records, announcements, reports, and services thanks to the technology. It is anticipated that the technology will speed up the duty officers' ability to respond to residents' needs. This allows the locals to use the system to electronically complete the necessary forms for barangay certificates. It is anticipated that the system's implementation will enhance the barangay's general services for its citizens.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to develop a centralized database through a community web-based management information system that will support the barangay local government unit in providing better assistance to its community. The project's overall goal is to design, develop, and implement a system that automates barangay services and resident transactions. In particular, the study aims to develop a portable system that can be accessed anytime and anywhere, via an internet connection and transferred from one device to another with no loss of functionality, for as long as it is accessed via web browsers, to make a system that stores all the residence information, blotter records and barangay officials' information through database, and to improve the portability of data processing and organization in the barangays by allowing users to simply use their devices to access the system.

Methodology

Research Methods

Information is gathered using the descriptive-qualitative method from a variety of sources, including surveys and observations. The researchers used descriptive qualitative methods to collect as much information as they could to record every step of the process. This approach can collect all the data that the researchers needed to input into the suggested system. The following techniques were used by the proponents to collect data:

Survey. During the requirements gathering stage, the researchers conducted a face-to-face survey to the residents of barangay for end users and professionals for expert users who provided resources on the flow of the existing system in the barangay.

Observation. To gather more information about how to develop the proposed system, the researchers have carried out some inspections of the barangay's current system. This observation led the researchers to identify a few problems that needed to be resolved to enhance the procedure in the barangay.

Project Design

The community web-based management system was created to assist the community with their technological needs. Its features include not only gathering and storing data and creating blotter records but also issuing barangay documents and data analytics. These data is intended to assist barangay officials with transactions based on their data analysis, which may be viewed in the dashboard. The system’s complete and innovative features provide convenience to its users. This feature is only available to users who have already registered in the system and may be verified by the system administrator, when the information is checked.

Web Designing Tool

Researchers used Bootstrap in web designing because of its various templates that can be edited based on their desired outcome. It consists of CSS and HTML that the researchers are familiar to utilize. The template is edited based on the requirement set by the client. It includes the background, fonts, buttons, and many others. Bootstrap is indeed an effective tool in accomplishing the requirements of the system.

Hypertext Preprocessor or Php is used by the researcher to the system for the functionalities of its features. This language supports the ability of the system to do its work according to what it should be. One of the examples are the buttons, which the Php supported to work. The researchers used MySQL as a tool for database making. This tool is known for its flexible and reliability in data protection. MySQL helps the system in storing all the data that is encoded to it. It helps the system to also record all the reports needed, which provides users have convenience upon using it.

Context Flow Diagram

Figure 1. Context Flow Diagram

Figure 1 shows the flow of the system beginning from when the admin logs in to the system and accessing the following settings: barangay, blotter, certificates, attendance, permit, and residence. Then, the statistical records are inputted in the system. Next is to process resident information. After the data and reports are encoded, they are automatically stored in the database and ready for printing. Lastly, the administrator creates reports at the conclusion of each transaction that are utilized to create annual statistical reports.

Agile Project Management Methodology

The researchers chose Agile Project Management methodology to show the phases on how the system can be created. It is iterative which can go along with the process until it produces the desired outcome. This can be used as a guide in the completion of the project through its step-by-step phases. This can also help generate new ideas that can be added to their project.

Phase 1: Requirements. During this process, the researchers interviewed a professor to determine the requirements needed. Next, the problem identified and solved using the system. After planning, the researchers proceeded to the brainstorming stage where they visualized the design of the system so that its features will meet the requirements needed.

Phase 2: Design. The researchers use different languages to design the system. Bootstrap was used for the design, Php for the backend coding, and MySQL for the database making. These languages were deemed to be very helpful for them to achieve their desired outcome.

Phase 3: Develop. The researchers began to implement the plans they brainstormed. Upon implementing it to the system, the possible outcomes were seen and whether the system they created is what they and their client visualized can be checked.

Phase 4: Test. The researchers tried the system. In this phase, the researchers tested the correctness of the languages used and checked whether the features of the system are functioning. During this phase, it was identified whether the requirements given by the client are met. The usability testing was used to assess the system.

Phase 5: Deploy. The researchers checked whether the system is working according to planned. The functionality of the system features can be checked. The client then reviewed the system to check if it meets the requirements and expectations.

Project Implementation and Evaluation

The phases in Agile Project Management guided them in project implementation. Its first phase where they identified their objective and plan on how to create the system is the basis for them to proceed to the second phase, in which they designed the system according to how it was visualized. In the third phase, the researchers implemented all the things they did in the first and second phase. In the fourth phase, the researchers tested the initial output. The last phase involves checking whether the system worked or not. This part of the study also shows how the researchers applied all the languages. It showed if the requirements set by the client are met.

The crucial part of this project is that after implementing all the things needed, the researchers tested (phase 4) the system to see if the expected outcome is achieved. The researchers planned and determined the goals in creating the system. Since the researchers used the usability testing, it will be conducted onsite. If the first attempt fails, the same people involved will be involved in the second attempt. The researchers identified three sets of participants. Each set is composed of three people who tested the system. In this part, the researchers created a realistic scenario involving the chosen participants. This attempted to test if the system is ready to be used in real-life situations. The researchers let its participants to test the system by:

- a. opening the system in a laptop or desktop with the power of Internet connection;
- b. testing its features, such as the collection of information to see if it can really store data, save data, or issue a document in a convenient way; and
- c. opening the system to other devices, such as mobile phones or tablets using web browsers to see if there are changes in its features.

After three sets of tests, the researchers analyzed and evaluated if the system is functioning based on the clients' requirements. In this part, the researchers identified the issues and the things for improvement. The researchers conducted a first-hand trial and tested all the features of the system. The process was documented through screen recording. The researchers tested the system to see if all its features are working according to its functions. The system was also shown to the client to be evaluated. Upon testing the system, researchers evaluated and determined the things for improvement to meet client's expectations.

System Evaluation

The evaluation procedure is conducted by IT and non-IT professionals. The respondents filled out a questionnaire to rate and evaluate the system. Each respondent is ranked on a five-point scale for each of the questions used by the researchers.

Table 1. Level of Satisfaction

Range	Scale Values	Interpretation
5.00 – 4.50	5	Highly Acceptable
4.49 – 3.50	4	Acceptable
3.49 – 2.50	3	Moderately Acceptable
2.49 – 1.50	2	Not Acceptable
1.49 – 1.00	1	Highly Unacceptable

Table 1 shows the value range of 5.00 – 4.50 as the highest rating and is interpreted as Highly Acceptable, whereas the value range of 1.50 – 1.00 has the lowest rating and is interpreted as Not Acceptable. As a result, since 2.51 is the value that indicates the project's viability, the overall result of this project is anticipated to be 2.51 or higher. The evaluation criteria used a numerical scale, with a maximum score of five and a minimum score of one. After the system has been put through an ISO 9126-compliant test, the system is rated based on the feedback from the respondents.

The respondents are from various barangays, who are residents of the City of Bacoor. The system was evaluated by 80 end users (barangay residents, and employees) and 20 expert users (mostly from outside the school) from the IT industry department, and some of the barangay officials of Alapan 1-C, for a total of 100 respondents. The mean is calculated by summing all the scores and dividing it by the number of respondents. The population is equal to x multiplied by the number of scores, according to the formula. If the scores are from a sample, the mean is referred to as the population.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 displays the evaluation response in the functionality criteria. In terms of end users, the system received an average mean of 4.67 from the 80 respondents, resulting in a rating of Highly Acceptable. According to the data, the respondents agreed that the accuracy of the system's output is most likely to be highly acceptable, with a score of 4.85, while the security standards has the lowest mean, with a score of 4.60. The researchers concluded that the data for the project's functionality provided accurate data and information based on the project's ability to perform under the modules' purposes. In terms of expert users, the system got an overall mean of 4.39 which included in the rating of Acceptable. The data shows the respondents conceded that the Functionality Compliance of the system overall gained 4.45, which is interpreted as Acceptable. The system's Security when the connections are down is the least acceptably with a mean data of 4.30.

Table 2. Evaluation of the System in Terms of Functionality

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Functionality	Mean	Remarks	Functionality	Mean	Remarks
The system does what was proposed correctly (e.g., printing and emailing reports based on user-applied filters). (Accuracy)	4.85	Highly Acceptable	The system produces accurate result. (Accuracy)	4.40	Acceptable
The system produces accurate tasks assigned to it (e.g., data request, print, data entry, update, and deletion). (Suitability)	4.58	Highly Acceptable	The system has operations used for specified tasks. (Suitability)	4.40	Acceptable
The system interacts with the specified modules (e.g., a combination of numbers, alphabets, symbols). (Security)	4.60	Highly Acceptable	The system has an internal backup restore routine. (Security)	4.30	Acceptable
The system can be performed in other devices without hustle (e.g., reports, email notifications, etc.). (Interoperability)	4.65	Highly Acceptable	The system interoperability is observed. (Interoperability)	4.40	Acceptable
The system uses password to secure access (e.g., incorrect login credentials, invalid request, and data entry). (Functionality Compliance)	4.70	Highly Acceptable	The system password encryption method works well with the program. (Functionality Compliance)	4.45	Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.67	Highly Acceptable		4.39	Acceptable

Table 3 displays the evaluation responses in terms of reliability. In terms of end users, the system received an overall mean of 4.70 from the 80 respondents, which is interpreted as Highly Acceptable. According to the data, the respondents agreed that the system's recoverability is the most highly acceptable, with a score of 4.78, while the system's maturity and operational consistency is the least acceptable, with a mean of 4.65. The researchers built the results of the data for the project's reliability and notified users based on the project's reliability to comply, maintain its stability, and accuracy. In terms of the expert users, the system has an overall mean of 4.13 which is included in the rating of Acceptable. The data shows that maturity, recoverability, and response to error gained an overall mean of 4.20. The majority of the software's flaws have been minimized over time, which is particularly significant. It also shows that the respondents conceded that the operational consistency has the least acceptability with a mean of 3.95.

Table 3. Evaluation of the System in Terms of Reliability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Reliability	Mean	Remarks	Reliability	Mean	Remarks
The system has the capability to record the information (e.g., recovering accidentally deleted data). (Recoverability)	4.78	Highly Acceptable	The system has the capability to recover the data even offline. (Recoverability)	4.20	Acceptable
The system has the capability to validate wrong input by users. (Fault Tolerance)	4.72	Highly Acceptable	The system is capable of recovering data in the event of failure. (Fault Tolerance)	4.10	Acceptable
The system has stability in operating an output (e.g., page loading speed, data request and entry, email sending, and report printing). (Operational Consistency)	4.65	Highly Acceptable	The system can perform well with quality upon the use of its operations. (Operational Consistency)	3.95	Acceptable
The system has the ability to respond to errors. (Maturity)	4.65	Highly Acceptable	The system can perform well without errors. (Maturity)	4.20	Acceptable
The system notifies the users concerning invalid data entry. (Response to Error)	4.70	Highly Acceptable	The system can respond well to any error. (Response to Error)	4.20	Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.70	Highly Acceptable		4.13	Acceptable

Table 4. Evaluation of the System in Terms of Usability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Usability	Mean	Remarks	Usability	Mean	Remarks
The software's display screen is well-organized and easy to understand, based on the user's expectations (e.g., displaying statuses and instructions). (Understandability)	4.70	Highly Acceptable	The system can sustain the route to be seen adequately. (Understandability)	4.45	Acceptable
The system has the capability to enable the user to learn its application (e.g., accessing modules and sub-modules and performing operations). (Learnability)	4.77	Highly Acceptable	The system can empower the client become familiar with its application. (Learnability)	4.40	Acceptable
The system performs according to the command with complete accuracy (e.g., using the system with different browsers). (Operability)	4.57	Highly Acceptable	The system is easy to operate and can be used without much effort. (Operability)	4.45	Acceptable
The system components ability is used with ease (e.g., system design, navigation, usability). (User-Friendliness)	4.71	Highly Acceptable	The system can operate its components with accuracy. (User-Friendliness)	4.40	Acceptable
The system has the capability to stick with its convenience guidelines. (Usability Compliance)	4.81	Highly Acceptable	The system has the capability to adhere to with usability standards. (Usability Compliance)	4.45	Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.71	Highly Acceptable		4.43	Acceptable

Table 4 shows the evaluation response in the usability criteria. In terms of end users, the system received an average mean of 4.71 from the 80 respondents, resulting in a rating of Highly Acceptable. According to the data, the respondents agreed that the system's ease of study and ability to adhere to usability standards are at the most acceptable, with a score of 4.81, while operability of the system is at the least acceptable, with a score of 4.57. The researchers concluded that the data for the project's usability provided usability compliance based on the project's simplicity of the GUI and user friendliness. In terms of expert users, the system got an overall mean of 4.43, which is interpreted as Acceptable. The data shows 4.45 as the most acceptable in operability, usability, and compliance and it also concluded that user-friendliness with 4.06 is the least acceptable.

Table 5. Evaluation of the System in Terms of Efficiency

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Efficiency	Mean	Remarks	Efficiency	Mean	Remarks
The system can quickly respond to commands (e.g., page loading, form submissions, data requests). (Time Behavior)	4.65	Highly Acceptable	The navigation elements of the system allow the user to move from page to page easily. (Time Behavior)	4.45	Acceptable
The system and its results are reliable and utilize resource efficiently (e.g., providing the user with the expected output/results/reports). (Resource Behavior)	4.56	Highly Acceptable	The system allows us to generate new knowledge. (Resource Behavior)	4.40	Acceptable
The system has the capability to perform its functions (e.g., run operations based on user requests). (Effectiveness)	4.73	Highly Acceptable	The system has the capability to perform its expected module. (Effectiveness)	4.45	Acceptable
The system has the capability to meet the client's requirements (e.g., data request, data entry, and report generation). (Efficiency Compliance)	4.56	Highly Acceptable	The system has the capacity to fulfill the client's expectations. (Efficiency Compliance)	4.55	Highly Acceptable
The system capability to respond according to its abilities. (Timeliness)	4.62	Highly Acceptable	The system responds within a short time and accordingly. (Timeliness)	4.45	Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.64	Highly Acceptable		4.46	Acceptable

Table 5 displays the evaluation response in the efficiency criteria. In terms of end users, the system received an average mean of 4.64 from the 80 respondents, resulting in a rating of Acceptable. According to the data, the respondents agreed that the system's efficiency in meeting the system's effectiveness is at the most acceptable with a score of 4.73, whereas the system's resource behavior and efficiency compliance are at the lowest highly acceptable with a score of 4.65. The researchers concluded that the data for the project's efficiency provided effectiveness based on the project's quick response and the project's ability to comply with user requirements.

In terms of expert users, the system got an overall mean of 4.46 which is interpreted as Acceptable. The data found effectiveness with the highest mean of 4.55 and interpreted as Highly Acceptable, while the resource behavior is interpreted as Acceptable with a mean of 4.40. The use of resources is a technique of monitoring how diverse computer system resources are involved when doing a performance test. Any strategy that permits a company or other company to optimize the usage of the result more quickly than to reduce flaws.

The evaluation response in the maintainability criteria is shown in Table 6. In terms of the end users, the system received an average mean of 4.56, resulting in a rating of Acceptable. According to the data, the respondents agreed that the system's Changeability is the most highly acceptable, with a score of 4.66, while the system's maintainability compliance is the least highly acceptable, with a mean of 4.52. The researchers hypothesized that the data for the project's maintainability provided stability and compliance based on the project's determining capability of enhancements and system errors. In addition, the system got an overall mean of 4.48 for expert users, which is interpreted as Acceptable. The data shows that maintainability compliance gained an overall mean of 4.65. It also shows that the respondents identify that changeability and testability gained the least rating with a mean of 4.40.

Table 6. Evaluation of the System in Terms of Maintainability

End Users (n=80)			Expert Users (n=20)		
Maintainability	Mean	Remarks	Maintainability	Mean	Remarks
The system information is clear (e.g., displaying error messages and warnings). (Analyzability)	4.53	Highly Acceptable	The system has edit features to modify any work. (Analyzability)	4.45	Acceptable
The system ability to open for changes (e.g., adding/creating, updating, deleting, and recovering data). (Changeability)	4.66	Highly Acceptable	The system can be upgraded/levelled-up as the need arises. (Changeability)	4.40	Acceptable
The system is built with perfection to make the stability of the system safe from hackers (e.g., system accessibility during updates). (Stability)	4.53	Highly Acceptable	The system features are safe from hackers. (Stability)	4.50	Highly Acceptable
The system is equipped with safety features and passwords (e.g., operations are running as expected). (Testability)	4.58	Highly Acceptable	The system has a combination of letters and numbers for better privacy protection. (Testability)	4.40	Acceptable
The system feature can be maintained in long term (e.g., data loss prevention). (Maintainability Compliance)	4.52	Highly Acceptable	The ability of the system to access in different variety of devices. (Maintainability Compliance)	4.65	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.56	Highly Acceptable		4.48	Acceptable

Table 7. Evaluation of the System Summary

Category	End-User	Expert-User	Variance (%)	Over-All Rating	Remarks
Functionality	4.67	4.39	0.28%	4.53	Highly Acceptable
Reliability	4.70	4.13	0.57%	4.41	Acceptable
Usability	4.71	4.43	0.28%	4.57	Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	4.64	4.46	0.18%	4.55	Highly Acceptable
Maintainability	4.56	4.48	0.08%	4.52	Highly Acceptable
Average	4.66	4.38	0.28%	4.52	Highly Acceptable

Table 7 shows the evaluation average mean by the end users, which is 4.66, and expert users with a mean of 4.38. In terms of the level of satisfaction, it shows that respondents are satisfied with the system's usability, and least satisfied with its reliability. The average overall level of satisfaction is 4.52, which is rated Acceptable, and the overall result for the variance percentage is 0.28% percent. Based on results, the researchers satisfied the end users' demands in terms of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, and maintainability with ratings of Highly Acceptable.

Conclusions

The researchers developed a browser-based system Barangay Management System with Community Charge Sheet Hotspotting, which stores all the residence information, blotter records, and barangay officials' information through database. With an assessment survey from 100 respondents, 80 of whom are end users and 20 expert users. Thus, the researchers conclude that the study successfully tackled the challenges of creating a portable system that guarantees access anytime, anywhere through an internet connection. It ensures high accuracy, reliability, and seamless transfer between devices while utilizing centralized and structured guidance modules. The system remains fully functional when accessed via web browsers, without any loss of functionality. The flow of information was achieved in terms of functionality and efficiency through detailed data analytics of citizen profiling, in which authorized personnel can maximize community awareness via proponents proposed browser-based systems.

The system efficiently and effectively stores all resident information, blotter records, and barangay officials' data by utilizing a database. The project's efficiency, maintainability, and reliability requirements are met by using ISO 9126 as a system evaluation tool, with the administrator and user accepting the system's set of modules, functionalities, and performance as moderately acceptable in terms of using the browser-based system. As a result, the project has been completed and is now ready for deployment and execution. The developed system may be implemented in the barangay to improve their transactions and make accurate results. Enhancement of the system's timeliness and completeness aspect should be taken into consideration to ensure its functionality. A follow-up study is encouraged to test level of the effectiveness and capabilities of the developed system.

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